

Understanding the Sixth Schedule of the Constitution and its Working in Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR) of Assam, India

Dr. Lienkhomang Changsan

Designation: Assistant Professor, Deptt. Of Political Science, Jengraimukh College

e-Mail ID: lienmangc@gmail.com

Abstract

The provision of Sixth Schedule was the creation of the Bordoloi Committee headed by Late Gopinath Bordoloi, the first chief minister of Assam. It was implemented in Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram and Tripura to provide autonomy and to initiate development efforts in the region. The main objective of the Sixth Schedule was to provide self-rule to the tribal communities in the hill areas of Assam. However, the region's institutional and structural growth was not provided by the Sixth Schedule. In 2003, the Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC) was established in Assam by an amendment to the Sixth Schedule and the autonomous structure intended for the governance of highland tribal territories in Northeast India. This essay aims to understand how the Sixth Schedule operates while also assessing the extent to which Bodoland residents have benefited from the provision of self-rule in resolving their administrative problems.

Keywords: Backward, BTC, Development, Sixth Schedule, Tribal.

Introduction

Tribal areas in northeastern India have long proven problematic to administer. The Northeast region is home to a number of tribal communities. Every tribal community has a distinct district identity, customs, traditions, and legal system. In light of this, the Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution contains unique provisions for the administration of tribally dominated areas, particularly in the North Eastern states of Assam, Tripura, Mizoram, and Meghalaya.

The Sixth Schedule established Autonomous District Councils to safeguard the economic and cultural interests of the hill tribes. It was enacted in 2003 in the plain regions with the establishment of the Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC) to govern Bodo-dominated areas following an extensive campaign for autonomy and separatist violence. Although the Sixth Schedule was enacted to provide self-governance and promote development in the region, it has yielded a mixed consequence of progress and stagnation. This paper is an attempt to study the working and implementation of the schedule in Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR), popularly known as Bodoland.

Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution

Following independence, the indigenous people of the northeastern hill regions demanded improved position under the constitutional framework and regional autonomy. The Indian government established a Constituent Assembly sub-committee to protect their tribal interests and guarantee their involvement in decision-making. The recommendations of the North East Frontier (Assam) Tribal and Excluded Areas Sub-committee, also known as the "Bordoloi Subcommittee," which was established under the direction of Gopinath Bordoloi, the first Chief Minister of Assam, served as the foundation for the Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution. Article 244(2) of the Indian Constitution states that the Sixth Schedule contains provisions for the governance of tribal territories in Assam, Meghalaya, Tripura and Mizoram. Passed by the Constituent Assembly in 1949, Sixth Schedule seeks to safeguard the rights of tribal population through the formation of Autonomous District Councils (ADCs). The main purpose behind the formulation of Sixth Schedule is to facilitate tribal communities with the power of administration of tribal areas within North East. The regions and population under tribal areas are being governed by Autonomous Districts and Regions irrespective of less intervention of state

legislatures. Sixth Schedule supports developing a framework related to autonomous decentralized governance that includes executive and legislative powers. Such powers effectively resolves the issues related to culture, customs, water, land and soil.

Councils established under the Sixth Schedule are also provided with judicial powers so that issues related to criminal or civil cases can be resolved. Therefore it has been identified that councils within Sixth Schedule are allocated with more powers as compared to local government based on the 73rd and 74th amendment made within the country. It has been identified that autonomy paradigm has helped to maintain the equilibrium within tribal communities through dispute resolution with the help of customary laws as well as control over facilities like money lending. Autonomous councils within Mizoram, Tripura and Assam holds the power to make decisions on whether there should be involvement of state legislations should be applied to their territories or not. Autonomous district councils possess executive powers and functions which is effective in managing the primary schools, roads, water ponds, administration of villages, forest, land revenue and many areas under the similar aspect under Sixth Schedule (Constitutional Provision).

A further amendment was made in the Sixth Schedule of the constitution in 2003 to meet the demands of a plain tribe of Assam under Sixth Schedule to the Constitution (Amendment) Act, 2003. It came when Government of India signed the Memorandum of Settlement (MoS) with surrendered BLT leaders to form BTC. Sixth Schedule which was planned for the hill tribes had to amend because of demands from the Bodo community for separate state. Administrative powers were granted for local administration of the area with different set up. Bodos were granted the amended Sixth schedule, with fewer powers compared to their demands of statehood, almost after their two decades of ethnic mobilization and violence

Working and Implementation of Sixth Schedule in BTR

In order to have a vivid knowledge on the working and implementation of the BTR it is necessary to understand the power and functions and development of the region. Before understanding the merits and demerits of the implementation of the provisions we will look into the provisions of BTC accord which was signed in 2003 to accommodate the Bodo community

providing them a politico-administrative setup. The Council has legislative powers in respect of subjects transferred to it. The BTR also have executive, administrative and financial powers in respect of subjects transferred to it.

The Executive Council:

One person will serve as the Chief and another as the Deputy Chief of the Executive Council, which exists. The Executive Council will have sufficient representation from non-tribal members. For protocol reasons in the BTR region, the Chief and Deputy Chief of the Council will be regarded as the Cabinet Minister's equivalent, and the other Executive Members as the Assam's Minister's equivalent.

Powers and Functions of Bodoland Territorial Region:

The officers and staff associated with the delegated subjects working in the BTR area are completely under the BTR's jurisdiction, and they are capable of being transferred within the BTR region. Additionally, BTR will have the authority to nominate people to all positions within its jurisdiction in compliance with the Assam government's appointment guidelines. However, this clause will not apply to positions where hiring decisions are based on the Assam Public Service Commission's recommendation. BTR established a Central Selection Board, and appointments are made based on the Board's recommendations.

Bodoland Territorial Region Legislative Assembly:

A maximum of 46 members will make up the Bodoland Territorial Council. Of these, 40 will be chosen by adult suffrage, with 30 designated for Scheduled Tribes, 5 for non-tribal communities and 5 open to all communities. The remaining 6 will be chosen by the Governor, who will grant them the same rights and privileges as other members, including the ability to vote, from among the under-represented communities in the Bodoland Territorial Areas District, at least two of whom must be women.

The CEO or Principal Secretary of the Council, who must be an officer at least as high as the Principal Secretary to the Government of Assam, will carry out the Council's executive duties. Secretaries, Joint Secretaries, Deputy Secretaries, Under Secretaries, Superintendents, Senior Administrative Assistants, Junior Administrative Assistants, and others help the Principal

Secretary. The Principal Secretary/CEO of the Council will have the authority to sanction the Government of Assam, and the senior most officer of the department, preferably not below the rank of Additional Director, will have the authority to sanction the head of the department or heads of departments, including technical sanction. This individual may be appointed Director of the Council for that department.

The proportionate share for the Council is calculated by the State Government on the basis of the central fund/SOPD fund available after setting aside the funds required for earmarked sectors and the salary. Allocation thus determined is communicated to the Council for preparation of budget and annual operational/ action plan.

Formulation of Schemes:

Plans are created with consideration for the different developmental requirements of the region in order to eliminate the long-standing backwardness in this part of the state and to satisfy the aspirations of the local populace. The entrusted departments' knowledge is used in the plan formulation process, and elected officials or Executive Members must be involved in the scheme selection process. When preparing a scheme, the government's guidelines controlling its creation and implementation are also followed. To direct the development process in the BTR areas, a Planning and Development Board should be established, chaired by the Chief of Bodoland Territorial Region.

Development in BTAD

Funds for the region's development are flowing together with the council's expanding authority and responsibilities. The federal government's funding was used for development projects. Roads are being built, villages are being electrified, and the impoverished are receiving subsidies. Even though the national government is in charge of these amenities, they are appropriately implemented for the region's development. Northeast India, a popular tourist destination due to its natural beauty, may draw tourists from outside the area to discover its undiscovered splendor. In order to achieve this ecotourism, many programs were created to protect endangered species, particularly in the Baksa district of BTR's Manas National Park.

The Bodoland Territorial Region, with financial assistance of both the State and Central governments, has taken initiatives for all round development in term of some existing infrastructure and creating new and modern facilities within the jurisdiction of the Council. Through the Infrastructure Department, the region has seen a spurt in the construction of administrative buildings which are the houses of various departments of the Bodoland Territorial Region. Added to this, the huge strides forward taken by the other departments such as the Irrigation Department, the Public Work Department and the Land Revenue department which have greatly contributed to the rapid rate of infrastructural development, can be looked upon as the developing District Council. Under the Public Work Department, the construction of roads, culverts, Ring-Well, etc. are also constructed for the improvement of the transportation in order to boost the socio economic development.

BTR has developed in the infrastructural sector for providing people services in the social sector. There is the establishment of hospitals; construction of school buildings all around four districts has shown the development of the sector of health and education. For agricultural development, there are provisions from development blocks to supply seeds, machinery and agricultural subsidies for the needy farmers. Such initiative was taken and implementation has developed the agricultural sector in the areas of BTR.

Post Implementation Challenges of BTR

It is often asserted that large corporations are not investing in industry or growth because of the rise in insurgency and violent mobilizations. Similarly, violence between communities living in the area has also been observed since the BTC deal. In 2008 and 2012, there were two significant acts of violence that caused property damage and fatalities in the BTR area. One extremist organization has been neutralized by the sixth schedule's implementation, but the National Democratic Front of Bodoland's (NDFB) activities have increased. After BTR was established, there hasn't been much of an improvement in other areas, like education. Because of poor infrastructural facilities in the educational sector and the high cost of education, poor inhabitants of the region could not afford to educate their children. On the other hand, lack of higher educational institutions is also one of the great challenges of development in higher

education in these rural areas In BTR area, handloom is well known and it has potential in the domestic market and for export as well. But, lack of structured market, documentation of market change, insufficient raw material supply and lack of proper knowledge, handloom products has not touched the margin to compete in the market. If funds will be properly implemented by authority providing necessary information and knowledge to local people, handloom and other industry can boom in the region Lack of local and regional market has impeded in the development process by not providing the local traders and small scale producers to sell their product at good price.

The region's residents contend that there is not enough space for the production of agricultural products and that their land was taken away due to significant debt. Second, it is asserted that there is a problem with migration to the area, taking jobs from residents who lack the necessary skills. Therefore, it is evident from this perspective that while the region has some infrastructure development, it is not fully designed to raise the economic and social standing of the local population.

Conclusion:

It is clear from the discussion above that while the region has expanded its political climate and infrastructure; it has been unable to meet the economic and social requirements of its citizens. In order to provide basic medical amenities, roads and hospitals were built, disregarding the community's standard of living. Second, although education is essential to the region's growth, the facilities for BTR students are inadequate. In the area, there are schools with no instructors and no resources for children's further education.

Lack of higher educational institutions, increasing fees of education and privatization of educational sector has burdened the poor class of the area and, as a result, lack of proper education has impeded development in the region. Lack of proper education and knowledge has created misunderstanding/mistrust among communities in the conflict-ridden period which resulted in violence in the region. So, this paper concluded that instead of having infrastructural development in the region it could not develop to meet the aspirations and addressed the long-

standing grievances of the region. In order for the region to grow properly, the autonomous council and administration should handle matters related to social security, health, and education for the local communities.

REFERENCES

- (Baro, K. 2017). “Sixth Schedule and its Implementations: Understanding the case of Bodoland (BTAD) in Assam.” IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS), 22, (12), 05-09.
- (Basumatary, J. 2009) “Working of the Bodoland Territorial Council” M.Phil Dissertation. Dept. of P. Sc. NEHU, Shillong,
- (Bhattacharjee, C. 1996). Ethnicity and Autonomy Movement: Case of Bodo-Kacharis of Assam. New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
- (Brahma, S. 2014). Status of Tourism Development in Bodoland Territorial Area Districts. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications , 4 (6)
- (Choudhury, D. 2016). “The Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution with Special Reference to Bodoland Territorial Council of Assam (IJHSSS), III, (1), 165-173.
- (Singh, B. 2018). Assam’s Bodoland Territorial Council draws flak for land transfer policy. The Economics Times (Guwahati).
- (Singh, M., A. 2004). “Challenges before Bodo Territorial Council”. Economic and Political Weekly, 39, (8), 784-785. Retrieved from www.jstore.org/stable/4414666.
- (Verghese, B. G. 1996). India's Northeast Resurgent: Ethnicity, Insurgency, Governance, Development. New Delhi: Konark Publishers.
- Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC) Accord (2003) Retrieved From http://cdpsindia.org/btc_accord.asp
- Office of the Joint Director of Economics and Statistics Kokrajhar BTC, Assam: Department of Economics & Statistics, BTC
